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Real-Time Detection of GPS Dimming and Fraud Attacks in Unmanned Aerial Vehicles with Artificial Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

Uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs) are widely used for reconnaissance, surveillance, logistics operations, and agricultural monitoring. However, their firm reliance on GNSS-based navigation systems presents significant cybersecurity risks. This study aims to develop an artificial intelligence-based model capable of detecting GPS jamming and spoofing attacks simulated in a controlled test environment. The attack simulations were successfully executed using a software-defined radio (SDR) device, the HackRF One, and GNSS data were collected via a NEO-M8N GPS module integrated into a Pixhawk flight controller. The data collection process was conducted on an Ubuntu-based system using custom scripts, and the resulting dataset was analyzed using seven different machine learning algorithms. Among these, the XGBoost algorithm demonstrated the best performance, achieving 96.4% accuracy, 96.4% recall, 96.5% precision, and 96.4% F1-score. With a training time of approximately 1.03 seconds and a test time of 0.01 seconds, the model proved suitable for real-time applications. The developed AI-based system was integrated into the flight controller via a Raspberry Pi and successfully tested in real flight scenarios, enabling instant detection and response during an attack. In conclusion, the proposed approach offers a cost-effective, reliable, and field-compatible solution that enhances the cybersecurity of both civilian and military UAV operations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs) have emerged as transformative technologies in both global defense and civilian sectors, playing critical roles in reconnaissance, surveillance, logistics, disaster management, and infrastructure monitoring. These systems enhance operational efficiency by minimizing human error and enabling missions in geographically challenging environments. However, these advantages also bring increased dependency on complex electronic components—particularly Global Navigation Satellite Systems

(GNSS)—which introduces significant cybersecurity vulnerabilities. The weak, unauthenticated, and open nature of GNSS signals makes them susceptible to manipulation by malicious actors, thereby posing substantial risks to the safety and functionality of UAVs [1].

Figure 1: GPS Jamming and Spoofing Attack Scenario

In recent years, GPS jamming and spoofing attacks—frequently discussed in the literature—have emerged as among the most critical threats to UAV navigation and mission success. GPS jamming involves disrupting GNSS signals with powerful interference, causing receivers to lose signal acquisition. Conversely, GPS spoofing deceives the receiver by transmitting counterfeit signals, which mislead the UAV into navigating based on incorrect location data [2]. These attacks can lead to operational failures, financial losses, and leaks of sensitive information, particularly in military and public safety applications. Consequently, the development of an effective and real-time detection mechanism for such attacks is crucial [3].

To illustrate the potential impact of these attacks on UAV systems, a visual representation of a GPS-jamming and spoofing attack scenario is shown in Figure 1.

In this study, the effects of GPS jamming and spoofing attacks on UAV systems are analyzed comprehensively. Fake signal generation, realistic scenario creation, and evaluation using seven machine learning algorithms were performed. The experimental setup was built upon low-cost hardware and open-source software; XGBoost was identified as the most accurate and computationally efficient algorithm and was implemented on a Raspberry Pi platform. Field tests confirmed the system's high detection performance against both jamming and spoofing attacks, thereby enhancing UAV mission security.

2 UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLES AND AUTONOMOUS SYSTEMS

Driven by rapid technological advancements, uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs) have become indispensable components of modern military and civilian operations. These systems are classified by weight, range, and altitude, including micro, mini, tactical, and strategic UAVs. They are capable of completing designated missions without human intervention [4]. Their autonomous capabilities stem from the integration of advanced propulsion systems, GNSS-based navigation modules, sensor suites, and embedded software algorithms. Modern UAVs incorporate components such as BLDC motors, IMUs, telemetry modules, multispectral cameras, LIDAR sensors, and high-performance processors to achieve high stability and precision during operation [5].

Autonomous systems are integral to UAV technology, removing the human element from critical decision-making processes and minimizing operational errors. Artificial intelligence algorithms, image processing techniques, and deep learning models enhance situational awareness, enabling UAVs to make real-time decisions in complex environments. As a result, UAVs are equipped with functionalities such as object detection, obstacle avoidance, autonomous route planning, and dynamic task execution [6]. Their ability to

provide accurate, real-time data without human intervention has significantly increased their value in areas such as infrastructure inspection, agricultural monitoring, and emergency response [7].

However, this high level of autonomy is heavily reliant on the accurate positioning provided by GNSS technology. The weak nature of GNSS signals makes UAVs vulnerable to jamming and spoofing attacks, which can disrupt mission performance. Therefore, advanced solutions such as sensor fusion, redundant navigation systems, and AI-powered anomaly detection have become essential for the reliable operation of autonomous UAVs [8]. In this context, the detection system proposed in this study represents a critical step toward ensuring the safe and sustainable autonomy of UAV operations.

3 PRINCIPLES AND APPLICATION DOMAINS OF GNSS TECHNOLOGY

Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) are satellite-based technologies developed to provide positioning, velocity, and timing information worldwide. The fundamental principle of GNSS is trilateration, in which a receiver determines its position by communicating with at least four satellites. Systems such as GPS (USA), GLONASS (Russia), Galileo (European Union), and BeiDou (China) offer global coverage, delivering precise location data to millions of users [9]. In particular, dual-frequency GNSS receivers mitigate atmospheric distortions, enabling centimeter-level positioning accuracy [10]. Table 1 summarizes various GNSS frequency bands and their respective application areas.

Table 1 GNSS Frequency Bands and Their Application Areas

Band Name	Frequency (MHz)	Application Area
L1	1575.42	Civil GNSS, general navigation, aviation, mobile applications
L2	1227.60	Military and dual-frequency civil applications, RTK support
L3	1381.05	Nuclear detonation detection systems (NUDET)
L4	1379.913	Ionospheric correction and research
L5	1176.45	High-precision aviation and safety applications
L6	1278.75	Japanese QZSS system, signal enhancement, high accuracy
S-Band	2483.5 – 2500	Mobile GNSS applications, Galileo commercial services
C-Band	5010 – 5030	Alternative GNSS applications, high-accuracy data transmission
X-Band	7900 – 8400	Military radar systems, space, and satellite communications
Ku-Band	12.0 – 18.0 GHz	Satellite-based internet and radar systems
Ka-Band	26.5 – 40.0 GHz	High-frequency broadband satellite communications

GNSS technologies play a critical role not only in UAV systems but also across sectors such as maritime navigation, land transportation, logistics, agriculture, and disaster management. In precision agriculture, GNSS-based positioning systems support tasks such as crop health monitoring, irrigation optimization, and yield forecasting [11]. In construction and infrastructure projects, GNSS is employed for site progress tracking, terrain modeling, and structural inspections. Likewise, in disaster management, GNSS-based solutions significantly enhance search-and-rescue operations. These widespread uses have made GNSS technologies indispensable to modern society [12].

However, the ubiquity of GNSS also brings heightened security concerns. The low power of GNSS signals, their vulnerability to atmospheric attenuation, and the openness of their protocols create opportunities for attacks such as jamming and spoofing [13]. Autonomous platforms, such as UAVs, are particularly susceptible to such attacks, which may result in mission failure, navigational errors, or even crashes. Therefore, securing GNSS infrastructure, supporting it with alternative sensor systems, and developing AI-driven anomaly-detection mechanisms are vital to the sustainability of GNSS-based applications [14].

4 JAMMING AND SPOOFING THREATS IN GNSS SYSTEMS AND CURRENT MITIGATION APPROACHES

One of the fundamental vulnerabilities of GNSS-based navigation systems is their inherently low signal strength, which makes them highly susceptible to jamming attacks. Jamming attacks disrupt satellite signals by introducing powerful interference, rendering the receiver unable to distinguish legitimate GNSS signals [15]. This can lead to UAVs losing positional awareness, deviating from their autonomous routes, or activating emergency protocols. Notably, jamming attacks can be carried out with relatively low-cost equipment and can cover vast geographical areas, making them a frequently employed component of electronic warfare during military operations [16].

Traditional approaches to detecting jamming rely on high-cost hardware, such as spectrum analyzers and antenna arrays, that monitor signal power fluctuations and interference levels. However, integrating such equipment into UAV systems poses significant engineering challenges and is often economically unfeasible. Consequently, software-based detection algorithms and data-driven modeling techniques have gained prominence, offering more flexible and cost-effective protection by analyzing the statistical properties of signals [17].

Spoofing attacks, on the other hand, represent a more sophisticated threat. In spoofing, fake GNSS signals are transmitted with stronger power than the authentic signals, tricking the receiver into calculating an incorrect position. This manipulation can redirect UAVs or mislead them during critical missions. Conventional spoofing countermeasures include multi-antenna systems, carrier-phase measurements, or cryptographic codes. However, these methods often face limitations in terms of cost, complexity, and real-time processing capacity [18]. Table 2 presents real-world examples of GPS jamming and spoofing incidents and their impacts.

Table 2: GPS Jamming and Spoofing Attacks and Their Effects

Attack	Description	Impacts
RQ-170 Drone Capture	Iran landed a US drone by broadcasting fake GPS signals.	Military intelligence loss, technological security breach.
South Korean Ships	North Korea disrupted the ship's GPS, causing navigation errors.	Economic loss, maritime safety vulnerability.
Black Sea Spoofing Incidents	Russia manipulated GPS signals in the region.	Confusion in international traffic poses a security risk.
Truck Spoofing in China	Drivers faked location data for financial gain.	Logistics disruptions result in financial losses for companies.
Dubai Airport Deviations	Aircraft GPS was manipulated over the Persian Gulf.	Aviation safety threat, urgent navigation adjustments.
University of Texas Demonstration	Academics hacked a yacht's GPS to reroute it.	Proof of vulnerability of critical infrastructures.

In recent years, the trend in GNSS security research has shifted from traditional physical-layer defenses toward more adaptive and software-based approaches. Hardware-based solutions—such as dual-antenna systems, directional antennas, or spectrum sensors—are typically costly, heavy, and energy-intensive, limiting their applicability on mobile platforms [19]. As a result, researchers have focused on lightweight alternatives, particularly those involving artificial intelligence (AI)-supported signal processing and data-driven anomaly detection. Advanced statistical modeling and machine learning techniques offer promising capabilities for analyzing real-time signal variations in GNSS data streams [20]. Table 3 outlines various modern mitigation methods against GPS jamming and spoofing attacks.

Table 3 Security Countermeasures Against GPS Jamming and Spoofing

Mitigation Method	Effectiveness Level	Application Area	Description	Reference
Encrypted GNSS Signals	High	Military, Critical Civil Applications	Encrypted GNSS signals (e.g., P(Y), M-code, Galileo PRS) can only be decrypted by authorized receivers, significantly preventing spoofing attempts.	Kaplan, E. D., Hegarty, C. J. (2017). [21]
Multi-GNSS Usage	Medium-High	Civil, Military	Using multiple GNSS systems together (e.g., GPS, Galileo, GLONASS, BeiDou) can reveal inter-system inconsistencies, which help detect spoofing.	Dovis, F. (2015). [22]
Signal Strength Monitoring	Medium	Advanced GNSS Receivers	Spoofing signals typically cause sudden increases in signal strength. Receivers can monitor signal power and use threshold-based detection.	Humphreys, T. E. et al. (2008). [23]
Doppler Shift Detection	Medium	Research, Test Applications	Real GNSS satellites induce Doppler shifts due to orbital motion; spoofing transmitters broadcasting at constant frequencies can be detected this way.	Psiaki, M. L., Humphreys, T. E. (2016). [24]
GNSS/IMU Integration	Medium-High	Autonomous Systems, Flight Navigation	Cross-validating GNSS data with IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) sensor outputs provides redundancy and helps detect spoofing-related inconsistencies.	Joerger, M., Pervan, B. (2013). [25]

5 METHODOLOGY

The attack and detection methodology developed in this study is structured around four main stages. In the first stage, the UAV system was identified and monitored; its positional and communication data were analyzed to map out its operational structure. This step served as the basis for designing targeted attack scenarios.

In the second stage, a two-phase attack was carried out in a controlled test environment. Initially, a jamming method was used to turn off the GPS signal, effectively neutralizing the UAV's position verification mechanism. This was followed by a spoofing phase, during which the UAV was manipulated with counterfeit signals to redirect it to incorrect coordinates. This approach demonstrated the inherent vulnerabilities of GPS-based systems through experimentation.

In the third stage, the effects of the attacks were observed via the flight control interface. It was detected that the UAV deviated from its actual position and followed routes determined by the attacker. In the final stage, flight data were analyzed using machine learning algorithms to develop a highly accurate detection model. Model validation in a real system demonstrated the feasibility of the AI-based approach in field conditions.

This four-phase methodology provides a systematic framework for analyzing both the effects and security gaps associated with GPS-based attacks. A general overview of the process is presented in the flowchart in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the attack and detection model

6 DETECTION OF THE ATTACK USING MACHINE LEARNING

The algorithmic structure for the automatic detection of jamming and spoofing attacks primarily relies on anomaly detection and classification. A Python-based machine learning pipeline was developed, and several models were trained sequentially. The dataset was split into training (70%) and test (30%) sets. During the training phase, various algorithms, including AdaBoost, ANN, KNN, XGBoost, RFC, SVM, and CatBoost, were utilized and optimized through parameter grid search. This approach enabled the identification of the optimal hyperparameter combinations and helped minimize the risk of overfitting. Figure 6 illustrates the cloned features from the training dataset for the various attack classes.

Figure 6. Cloned features of attack classes in the training dataset

The purpose of this comprehensive analysis using machine learning algorithms was to determine the most operationally suitable model for protecting UAVs against GPS-based jamming and spoofing attacks. Each algorithm was evaluated based on multiple criteria, including accuracy, processing time, and classification performance. The goal was to identify a model that could deliver the fastest, most accurate response in real-time applications.

According to the results presented in Table 4, the Random Forest algorithm achieved the highest classification accuracy of 97.72%. However, the XGBoost model stood out with a competitive 96.40% accuracy, along with remarkably low test and training times of 0.0101 and 1.0273 seconds, respectively, offering significant speed advantages.

ANN and CatBoost also emerged as strong alternatives with accuracy scores of 91.25% and 93.24% respectively. However, their relatively longer training and test times reduced their practical applicability in real-time scenarios. Although theoretically robust, KNN and SVM models lag in processing speed and yield lower classification metrics, suggesting limited suitability for autonomous systems that require instant decision-making.

Ultimately, selecting a detection algorithm for these attack types must consider not only high accuracy but also low processing time, class separability, and resource efficiency. Particularly in autonomous and real-time applications, rapid decision-making is critical. In this regard, XGBoost emerged as the most balanced and appropriate solution, offering an effective alternative for real-time detection of GNSS-based attacks.

7 CONCLUSION

The experimental studies conducted demonstrate that GNSS-based UAV navigation systems are susceptible to significant security vulnerabilities against jamming and spoofing attacks. Interference and counterfeit signals generated via the HackRF One device directly impaired the UAV's positioning capabilities, thereby jeopardizing operational integrity. The telemetry data collected during these attacks contained critical indicators, including signal-strength anomalies, position deviations, and orientation errors. Integrating this data into machine learning models significantly enhanced the reliability of the real-time detection mechanism.

Among the seven machine learning models evaluated, the XGBoost algorithm achieved the highest accuracy (96.40%) and the shortest test time (0.0101 seconds), indicating its well-balanced architecture for both anomaly detection and attack classification. The system, integrated into a Raspberry Pi and deployed in field conditions, operated continuously on real-time telemetry streams during flights, successfully detecting both jamming and spoofing attacks and sending timely alerts to the ground control station. This provides clear evidence of the practical effectiveness of a low-cost, hardware-and-open-source-software-based architecture.

In conclusion, this study presents an innovative, flexible, and scalable solution for enhancing the cybersecurity of GNSS-based UAV systems. The developed system has the potential to mitigate security vulnerabilities in both military and civilian UAV operations. Furthermore, by integrating advanced technologies such as multi-sensor fusion and cloud-based data processing, the proposed architecture could be extended to a broader range of applications.

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